

High-capacitance BiPO₄ material with monoclinic/hexagonal crystalline phase heterostructure for aqueous asymmetric supercapacitors

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Fig. S1 Overview of the types and classification of anode materials for asymmetric supercapacitors

Fig. S2 Historic timeline for the development of anode materials for asymmetric supercapacitors

Fig. S3 (a-d) Rietveld refined XRD diffractograms for BP80, BP120, BP165 and BP180, respectively.

Fig. S4 XRD patterns of BP150-ethanol and BP150, correspondingly.

Fig. S5 (a, b) SEM-EDX elemental mapping of BP80 and BP180 samples, respectively.

Fig. S6 (a-e) CV curves for BP80, BP120, BP165, BP180 and Mixed respectively, at various scan rates.

Fig. S7 (a-e) GCD curves at different current densities for BP80, BP120, BP165, BP180 and Mixed samples, correspondingly.

Fig. S8 XRD measurement of NCP-350.

Fig. S9 (a, b) HRTEM images and (c) element mapping of NCP-350.

Fig. S10 (a) N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherm curves and (b) pore size distribution of NCP-350.

Fig. S11 (a-c) CV curves at various scan rates, (d-f) GCD curves at different current densities of NCP-300, NCP-350 and NCP-400, respectively.

Table S1 Comparison of electrochemical performances for NCP-350//BP150 ASC device with reported literatures

ASC device	Energy density (power density)	Current density	Capacitance	Electrolyte	Reference
Ni ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ ·8H ₂ O//AC	42.1 Wh kg ⁻¹ (160 W kg ⁻¹) 28.8 Wh kg ⁻¹ (4000 W kg ⁻¹)	0.2 A g ⁻¹ 5 A g ⁻¹	118 F g ⁻¹ 81 F g ⁻¹	6 M KOH	[24]
Co/NiPO ₄ -40//BiPO ₄	36.84 Wh kg ⁻¹ (254.52 W kg ⁻¹)	1 A g ⁻¹	264.3 F g ⁻¹	3 M KOH	[50]
CoNi ₂ (PO ₄) ₂ //AC	32.2 Wh kg ⁻¹ (377.6 W kg ⁻¹) 21.7 Wh kg ⁻¹ (4900 W kg ⁻¹)	1 A g ⁻¹	103 F g ⁻¹	2 M KOH	[51]
Ni _{1.38} Co _{1.62} (PO ₄) ₂ ·8H ₂ O//rGO	42.3 Wh kg ⁻¹ (1000 W kg ⁻¹) 36.7 Wh kg ⁻¹ (1700 W kg ⁻¹)	1.3 A g ⁻¹ 2.1 A g ⁻¹	120 F g ⁻¹ 103 F g ⁻¹	1 M KOH	[52]
Ni-CoPO ₄ //AC	33.6 Wh kg ⁻¹ (730 W kg ⁻¹) 19.5 Wh kg ⁻¹ (3250 W kg ⁻¹)	1 A g ⁻¹ 5 A g ⁻¹	166 C g ⁻¹ 108.5 C g ⁻¹	1 M KOH	[53]
NiCo(PO ₄) ₃ /Graphene Foam//AC	34.8 Wh kg ⁻¹ (377 W kg ⁻¹)	0.5 A g ⁻¹ 5 A g ⁻¹	45 mAh g ⁻¹ 12.5 mAh g ⁻¹	1 M KOH	[54]
NCP-350//BP150	98.17 Wh kg⁻¹ (846.49 W kg⁻¹) 39.29 Wh kg⁻¹ (6735.43 W kg⁻¹)	1 A g⁻¹ 15 A g⁻¹	260.95 F g⁻¹ 196.88 F g⁻¹	3 M KOH	This work